

Figure S1. Acid stability of S100 + alginate capsules produced without an oil-in-water emulsion core. Capsules were exposed to acidic buffers (0.2M NaCl + HCl) for 2 h at 37 °C before release in Sorensen's buffer (pH 7.5).

Figure S2. Release kinetics of S100 + alginate core-shell capsules immediately after production (control), after pH 1 (acid exposure) for 2 h and after 120s at 95 °C (heat exposure).